

Year	Main Topics Covered				Reference
	Electrocatalytic H ₂ generation	Photo-catalytic H ₂ generation	Porphyrin catalyst / chromophore utilization	Graphene-Related Material utilization	
2024					This work
2024					26
2023					27
2022					28
2022					29
2022					30
2021					31
2021					32
2021					33
2020					34
2019					35

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Review

Mini-Review on Catalytic Hydrogen Evolution from Porphyrin–Graphene Structures

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ABSTRACT: Porphyrin-based derivatives have been extensively investigated in photocatalytic, electrocatalytic, and photoelectrocatalytic H₂ production systems as both photosensitizers and catalysts. Recently, their combination with two-dimensional materials, such as graphene oxide, reduced graphene oxide, and graphene quantum dots, has attracted significant attention for hydrogen evolution due to the advanced electronic properties, good stability, and low-cost fabrication of these materials. This mini-review summarizes the recent developments concerning the application of porphyrin–graphene ensembles in catalytic H₂ generation. Current challenges concerning this application are discussed, and future perspectives are also proposed.

INTRODUCTION

From the onset of the Industrial Revolution, the extraction and utilization of fossil fuels, such as coal, petroleum, and natural gas, have significantly advanced human society. Nevertheless, the escalating global energy demand has led to widespread reliance on fossil fuels, giving rise to a range of challenging environmental problems.¹ These issues encompass global warming, acid rain, depletion of stratospheric ozone, and reduced biodiversity. Furthermore, the majority of fossil fuels fall into the category of non-renewable resources, and their reserves have undergone a substantial decline over the last decades.²

The escalating demand for energy along with the environmental challenges resulting from the overexploitation of fossil fuels render the imperative adoption of renewable, sustainable, and environmentally friendly energy sources. In seeking alternatives to the dependence upon fossil fuels in everyday applications, it is crucial that substitutes exhibit higher energy efficiency and, notably, lower ecological impact compared to the combustion of fossil fuels, particularly in terms of carbon emissions.³ Hydrogen emerges as a clean energy source with versatile applications, including automotive power, heating, fuel cells, and various others, offering a diminished environmental footprint because the only product from its combustion is molecular water.⁴ Moreover, the utilization of hydrogen as an alternative fuel represents a longstanding strategy for globally reducing carbon dioxide emissions.^{5,6}

H₂ as an energy carrier can be produced catalytically from water through either electrocatalytic, photocatalytic, or photoelectrocatalytic schemes (Figure 1). These processes, while theoretically simple, require efficient and cost-effective catalysts to achieve practical feasibility.^{7,8} The electrocatalytic hydrogen evolution reaction (HER) comprises two distinct processes

facilitating the generation of H₂ through H⁺ reduction at catalytic sites. In both pathways, because of the applied potential, initially, H⁺ undergoes reduction to form hydride (H⁻) species at catalytic centers. Afterward, either two hydride species react, releasing molecular hydrogen, or in the second pathway, a hydride reacts with a proton–electron couple, leading to H₂ formation.⁹

In photocatalysis, where no external potential is required, the initial step involves light absorption from the molecular or semiconductor photocatalytic component. This leads to the excitation of electrons to the lowest unoccupied molecular orbital (LUMO) or the conduction band (CB) level, respectively, and leaving holes in the highest occupied molecular orbital (HOMO)/valence band (VB) level. Efficient charge separation, redox reactions, and product desorption are crucial aspects for the HER. Optimal photocatalytic performance requires a photosensitizer with a suitable HOMO–LUMO gap/band gap for solar energy absorption, efficient charge carrier separation, and abundant active sites on the catalyst surface.^{5,10} The notable limitation of photocatalytic systems is the necessity of a sacrificial electron donor (SED) to complete the catalytic cycle. This problem can be overwhelmed by the construction of a photoelectrocatalytic device, where the necessary electrons are provided by an oxidative catalytic transformation at the

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Figure 1. Schematic illustration of hydrogen generation from water through (a) photocatalytic, (b) electrocatalytic, or (c) photoelectrocatalytic systems.

Table 1. Review Studies on Electrocatalytic and Photocatalytic Hydrogen Production

Year	Main Topics Covered					Reference
	Electro-catalytic H ₂ generation	Photo-catalytic H ₂ generation	Porphyrin catalyst / chromophore utilisation	Graphene Related Material utilisation	Semiconductor material utilisation	
2024						This work
2024						7
2023						38
2022						39
2022						40
2022						41
2022						10
2022						35
2021						42
2021						43
2021						44
2020						34
2019						45

photoanode, through the external circuit, to the cathode where H₂ is generated.^{11,12} Noteworthy, this approach could be efficient in the absence of externally applied potential because the light excitation (solar energy) will be used to overcome the required energy barrier.

Nanomaterials have emerged as key elements in constructing light-energy-harvesting systems,^{13,14} offering advantages, like large surface areas and diverse morphologies. Specifically two-dimensional (2D) materials have been widely employed in green hydrogen generation systems to improve the overall efficiency

Scheme 1. Chemical Structures of the Molecular Porphyrin Catalysts Utilized in Electrocatalytic H₂ Evolution in Combination with GRMs

and stability.^{15–18} Graphene, which stands out due to its exceptional conductivity, high surface area, optical transmittance, good stability, and low-cost fabrication, is as a versatile component for catalytic hydrogen production schemes.^{6,19} Graphene-related materials (GRMs) have already been extensively used for electrocatalytic^{20–27} and photocatalytic²⁸ HER systems, displaying outstanding activity.

These materials can undergo functionalization with molecular chromophores,²⁹ like porphyrins, through either covalent (i.e., amide coupling or coordination bonding) or non-covalent (i.e., π - π interactions) interactions.³⁰ This strategy enhances light absorption and reduces the electron-hole recombination, improving photocatalytic performance toward H₂ production.¹⁰ Additionally, it provides more active sites, i.e., metal ions with a stable coordination environment, which is beneficial for electrocatalytic H₂ formation.^{31–33} Porphyrin molecules are particularly well-suited for this type of modification due to their easily modifiable structure, various interaction mechanisms with materials, and high molar absorption coefficient in the visible region. Finally, the porphyrin macrocycle greatly enriches the redox chemistry of the metal centers, providing improved pathways for HER catalysis.^{9,34} In electrocatalytic HER, porphyrins serve as efficient catalysts due to their ability to stabilize different oxidation states of the central metal ion, facilitating proton reduction at relatively low overpotentials.³⁴ In photocatalysis, porphyrins act as light-harvesting agents, efficiently absorbing visible light and generating excited-state electrons that can drive the HER.³⁵

The integration of 2D carbon materials with porphyrin-based catalysts has garnered significant attention in the field of catalytic

HER. The unique electronic properties of 2D GRM offer a synergistic platform when combined with porphyrins.³⁶ This synergy arises primarily from the charge transfer interactions between the delocalized π -electron systems of graphene and the π -conjugated macrocyclic structure of porphyrins.³⁷ These interactions can modify the redox environment of porphyrins, thereby influencing their catalytic behavior. Understanding and controlling these charge transfer processes are crucial to optimizing the catalytic activity of these hybrid systems.

This scientific area has gained significant attention, which is illustrated by the number of existing reviews in the domain of catalytic hydrogen generation. Table 1 lists some representative reviews in the past 5 years. Most of the reviews are focused on the utilization of semiconductors, while there is no report highlighting the combination of the versatile porphyrin molecules with GRMs toward catalytic green hydrogen generation (Table 1). Therefore, the present mini-review fills this critical gap in the field by focusing on the synergistic effects between porphyrins and graphene and detailing how their combination leads to superior catalytic performance. This specific interplay and its benefits are often only briefly mentioned in other reviews that cover a wider range of materials.

Because the combination of GRM with porphyrin molecules has attracted substantial attention in sustainable energy research, this review summarizes the recent advances in electrocatalytic and photocatalytic HER from porphyrin-graphene ensembles. In the following sections, we will explore the latest advancements, the key factors that influence this catalytic transformation, the role of each catalytic component, current challenges and limitations, and promising prospects for the

development of efficient HER devices. Initially, we will delve into the application of modified GRM with porphyrin molecules for electrocatalytic H₂ evolution. Subsequently, our exploration will extend to analogous light-driven catalytic systems reported in the literature.

ELECTROCATALYSIS

Cobalt molecular catalysts for hydrogen production have been extensively investigated during the last decades, establishing their great potential in terms of both efficiency as well as stability.^{46–48} The first system of electrocatalytic H₂ evolution utilizing graphene oxide and a porphyrin molecular catalyst was published by Shen and co-workers and was inspired by the outstanding activity of cobalt complexes toward HER.⁴⁹ The authors developed multilayer catalytic films composed of electrochemically reduced graphene oxide (ERGO) and positively charged cobalt porphyrin [CoTMPyP]⁴⁺ (Scheme 1a). The preparation of the electrodes was achieved by layer-by-layer assembly of negatively charged GO and [CoTMPyP]⁴⁺ via electrostatic interactions, followed by an electrochemical reduction process. Several porphyrin deposition cycles were performed before the reduction process to investigate whether this parameter affects the catalytic efficiency. The resulting multilayer electrodes were tested in electrocatalysis and presented high H₂ production in alkaline media, while the Co–N₄ moiety of the cobalt porphyrin proved the catalytic active site. The best performing electrode (entry 1 in Table 2) was the electrode with 7 layers of [CoTMPyP]⁴⁺ ([ERGO@CoTMPyP]7). Noteworthy, electrocatalytic experiments at different pH demonstrated that the pH does not influence the activity of the system because minor variations were observed from pH 0 to 13. The same cobalt porphyrin was investigated by Ma et al., who simplified the preparation protocol and further improved the electrocatalytic activity of the CoTMPyP/ERGO nanocomposite (entry 2 in Table 2).⁵⁰

Expanding the research of cobalt tetrapyrrolic catalysts on GRMs, Cao and co-workers immobilized three cobalt corrole catalysts on graphene and applied the resulting materials in electrocatalytic hydrogen evolution in aqueous media.⁵¹ In detail, they synthesized corrole molecules Co-PPh₃, 1-Co-py, and 2-Co-py (Scheme 1b) and supported them on graphene to obtain catalytically active materials toward H₂ production, operating in different pH values (pH 0–14). Electrocatalysis results revealed the following performance trend: Co-PPh₃/G > 1-Co-py/G > 2-Co-py/G, demonstrating the significant role of the axial coordinating ligand as well as the pyrenyl peripheral substitution (entries 3–5 in Table 2).

The role of the metal ion inside the porphyrin core toward electrocatalytic H₂ evolution was investigated by Galo and co-workers.⁵² The researchers prepared glassy carbon (GC) electrodes, introduced oxo and pyridyl groups on their surfaces, and subsequently deposited octaethyl-metalated porphyrins (M-OEP; Scheme 1c). The electrodes were able to produce H₂ electrocatalytically at pH 7, while Co-OEP and Cu-OEP presented the highest activity (entries 6–8 in Table 2). Atomic force microscopy (AFM) and scanning electron microscopy (SEM) studies showed another significant parameter that influences the catalysis, namely, the formation of appropriate supramolecular architectures on the surface of the electrode, which enables proton diffusion electron transfer processes.

Lee and co-workers developed 2D assemblies of various metalated porphyrins on graphene to shed light into the molecular aspects that govern the mechanism of electrocatalytic

Table 2. Electrocatalytic Activity of Porphyrin–GRM Assemblies toward Hydrogen Evolution

entry	electrocatalyst	electrolyte	Tafel slopes (mV dec ⁻¹)	E _{onset} versus RHE (V)	current density (mA cm ⁻²)	overpotential, η (mV)	FE (%)	TON/TOF	reference
1	[ERGO@CoTMPyP]7	0.1 M KOH, pH 13.0	116			474			49
2	CoTMPyP/ERGO	0.1 M KOH, pH 13.0	99			347			50
3	Co-PPh ₃ /G	1.0 M KOH, pH 14.0		-0.45	166 at -0.90 V				51
4	1-Co-py/G	1.0 M KOH, pH 14.0		-0.45	100 at -0.90 V				51
5	2-Co-py/G	1.0 M KOH, pH 14.0		-0.45	73 at -0.90 V				51
6	GC pyridyl + Co-OEP	0.066 M phosphate buffer, pH 7.0	194				60	6400 TON	52
7	GC ox + Cu-OEP	0.066 M phosphate buffer, pH 7.0	103				61	3300 TON	52
8	GC + Cu-OEP	0.066 M phosphate buffer, pH 7.0	90				58	6500 TON	52
9	Fe-PMOF/PG	1.0 M KOH, pH 14.0	73.06	-0.034		154.71			55
10	Ni-PC[8]/ERGO	1.0 M KOH, pH 14.0		-0.020		360		27.5 mmol h ⁻¹ g ⁻¹ TOF	56
11	GO-PCOF	0.5 M H ₂ SO ₄	241			376			57
12	TPP-GO-ZnPc	0.5 M H ₂ SO ₄	153		10 at -0.518 V	518			54

Figure 2. Schematic illustration for the preparation of (a) TPP-GO-ZnPc⁵⁴ and (b) Fe-PMOF/PG. This figure was reproduced with permission from ref 55. Copyright 2018 Elsevier.

H_2 production.⁵³ More specifically, they investigated the tetraphenyl, tetrapyrrolyl, and tetraaminophenyl porphyrin molecules illustrated in Scheme 1d toward HER after their immobilization onto one layer of graphene. The authors point out the significance of the intermolecular H bonding between porphyrin molecules, the π -electron delocalization on the porphyrin macrocycle, and the electronegativity of the central N4 atoms, which assist the charge transfer to graphene. The Pt-metalated derivative presented the highest activity for H_2 evolution in all cases, while the peripheral substitution followed the trend: phenyl < pyrrolyl < aminophenyl. Between the M-porphyrin/graphene assemblies, the HER performance followed the order Zn < Ni < Pt.

In another approach, Wang et al. synthesized a hybrid material consisting of TAPP porphyrin units and zinc phthalocyanine units covalently linked to GO and applied this material in electrocatalytic H_2 generation. The three-component system was proven more efficient compared to the two-component hybrids (TPP-GO and ZnPc-GO), and this result was attributed to the strong electronic communication and charge transfer phenomena within the TPP-GO-ZnPc derivative. The authors point out the importance of simultaneous grafting of porphyrins and phthalocyanines onto GO as a promising approach for efficient electrocatalytic HER systems.⁵⁴

The research works described above deal with molecular HER catalytic moieties based on porphyrin derivatives, which were used in combination with 2D GRMs. There are few publications where 2D or three-dimensional (3D) porphyrin materials⁵⁸ were utilized instead. Guo and co-workers prepared a 3D porphyrin-metal-organic framework (PMOF) based on iron tetracarboxyphenyl porphyrin (Fe-PMOF) and, subsequently, introduced porous graphene via hydrothermal procedure, obtaining Fe-PMOF/PG (Figure 2).⁵⁵ The researchers

demonstrated that the utilization of the graphene substrate was beneficial to achieve a more stable, more conductive, and more electrocatalytically efficient material (entry 9 in Table 2).

Another type of 2D porphyrin material utilized toward HER application was porphyrin polymers. Tuncel and co-workers constructed a polymer network (PC[8]; Scheme 2a) via cross-linking tetra-aryl-substituted porphyrins and hydroxy-substituted cucurbit[8].⁵⁶ Subsequently, the researchers loaded nickel atoms on this network, coated GO, which was deposited on FTO, with Ni-PC[8], and reduced GO afterward electrochemically. The prepared electrodes varied in terms of Ni and reduced GO mass ratio versus the PC[8] network and were proven efficient electrocatalysts for hydrogen evolution (entry 10 in Table 2). In another report, covalent coupling of the 2D porphyrin polymer with GO enhanced the HER activity. Wang et al. synthesized the porphyrin covalent organic framework (PCOF; Scheme 2b) and covalently connected graphene oxide via amide bond formation utilizing the DCC coupling reagent.⁵⁷ The prepared GO-PCOF conjugate presented superior electrocatalytic HER performance (entry 11 in Table 2) compared to GO, PCOF, or molecular H_2 -TPP, demonstrating the influence of the covalent attachment to the overall catalytic activity.

The recent publications reviewed above dealing with electrocatalytic H_2 production from porphyrin-graphene ensembles have pointed out the significant factors that influence this catalytic transformation. These factors include

- the metal ion inside the porphyrin macrocycle, which in most cases is the catalytic center
- the coordination sphere of the metal porphyrin center
- the peripheral substitution of the molecular porphyrin catalyst

Scheme 2. Chemical Structures of the Porphyrin Polymer Networks PC[8]⁵⁶ and GO-PCOF,⁵⁷ Utilized as Catalysts in Electrocatalytic H₂ Evolution

- the electronic communication between the π systems of GRM and the porphyrin macrocycles
- the formation of 2D or 3D porphyrin materials and the subsequent incorporation of GRMs (i.e., PMOF and PCOF)
- the different oxidation states of GRMs, namely, GO, ERGO, etc.
- the electrolyte and pH of the reaction
- the surface supramolecular architectures of the electrode

■ PHOTOCATALYSIS

The catalytic transformation of protons to molecular H₂ can be boosted via either the assistance of an applied overpotential or

the utilization of solar energy. This paragraph reviews the publications targeting photocatalytic H₂ evolution from porphyrin photosensitizers/catalysts and GRMs.

The first report on this field was published by Yang and co-workers in 2013, who immobilized tetra-hydroxy porphyrin pTHPP (Scheme 3a) on rGO and investigated the morphological and electronic properties of the resulting hybrid material.⁵⁹ Subsequently, the researchers deposited Pt NPs on the pTHPP/rGO hybrid and applied it in light-driven H₂ evolution using triethylamine as the SED. The important role of reduced graphene oxide as an electron mediator, preventing photoinduced electron–hole recombination, was established. In an effort to increase both the stability and the efficiency of this

Scheme 3. Chemical Structures of (a) pTHPP,⁵⁹ (b) [ZnTMPyP]⁴⁺,⁶⁰ and (c) DPyPP⁶¹ Porphyrin Derivatives Utilized as Photosensitizers for the Photocatalytic Transformation of Protons to Molecular Hydrogen^a

^aDPyPP-M-GO is a schematic illustration of graphene oxide implanted with metal ions and linked through the DPyPP chromophore molecules.

system, a surfactant molecule (CTAB) was introduced, and indeed, it was proven beneficial toward H₂ production (entry 1 in Table 3).

In another report, Yuan et al. used water-soluble porphyrin [ZnTMPyP]⁴⁺ (Scheme 3b) as a light-absorbing moiety together with 2D material MoS₂/rGO as the catalytic moiety and developed a heterogeneous system for efficient H₂ production.⁶⁰ Noteworthy, this is a rare photocatalytic example where the photosensitizer and catalyst are in different states (solution versus dispersion). Upon visible light irradiation and in the presence of TEOA as the SED, the system reached 2560 μmol g⁻¹ h⁻¹ of H₂ production (entry 2 in Table 3). Mechanistical investigation demonstrated that, after light excitation, the porphyrin-chromophore is quenched by MoS₂/rGO following an oxidative quenching.

An alternative approach for the introduction of porphyrins on the surface of graphene oxide involves attaching metal ions to GO, which can serve as interfacial linkers. The attachment of porphyrin molecules can be achieved via either electrostatic interactions or coordination bonding. For this purpose, several metal cations (K^(I), Ca^(II), Zn^(II), Cu^(II), Co^(III), and Cr^(III)) were implanted onto graphene oxide forming the M-GO material.⁶¹ The subsequent introduction of DPyPP porphyrin (Scheme 3c) was accomplished by simply mixing modified graphene oxide with the DPyPP chromophore. The researchers continued with

the photocatalytic investigation toward H₂ production using triethylamine as the SED and showed that the catalytic activity follows the order GO < DPyPP-GO < DPyPP-Cr^(III)-GO (entries 3–5 in Table 3). The high performance of the DPyPP-Cr^(III)-GO photocatalyst was attributed to the strong coordination interaction between metal ions and porphyrin, while the role of the porphyrin molecule was to absorb the visible light, and the graphene oxide served as the electron mediator. The metal ions were proven beneficial for the promotion of the photogenerated electrons, thus improving the overall performance. The same group further explored this field with the utilization of another metal ion, namely, Co^(II), and prepared the DPyPP-Co^(II)-GO photocatalytic material (Scheme 3c).⁶² The photocatalyst was able to produce H₂ without the need of other co-catalysts, outperforming the previous systems (entry 6 in Table 3). The researchers verified that Co^(II) ions promote electron propagation between the porphyrin moiety and graphene oxide, improving the overall activity of the system. With the above results in hand, the same group prepared DPyPP-Co-GO, which, instead of cobalt ions, contained metallic Co nanoparticles, with the aim to achieve further improved catalytic performance because of the co-catalytic function of the NPs.⁶³ Indeed, the observed visible-light-driven H₂ evolution of DPyPP-Co-GO was doubled in comparison to DPyPP-Co^(II)-GO after 2 h of irradiation

Table 3. Photocatalytic Activity of Porphyrin–GRM Assemblies toward Hydrogen Production

entry	PS/photocatalyst	catalyst	SED	solvent	light source	irradiation time (h)	TON/TOF	reference
1	pTHPP/rGO	Pt-NPs	TEA (10 vol %)	H ₂ O (CTAB)	150 W Xe lamp	5	11.2 mmol g ⁻¹ TOF	59
2	[ZnTMPyP] ⁴⁺ /MoS ₂ /RGO		TEOA	H ₂ O	300 W Xe lamp		2.56 mmol g ⁻¹ h ⁻¹ TOF	60
3	GO		TEOA (10 vol %)	H ₂ O	300 W Xe lamp	8	137 μmol g ⁻¹ TOF	61
4	TPPy-GO		TEOA (10 vol %)	H ₂ O	300 W Xe lamp	8	686 μmol g ⁻¹ TOF	61
5	DPyP-Co ^(III) -GO		TEOA (10 vol %)	H ₂ O	300 W Xe lamp	8	928 μmol g ⁻¹ TOF	61
6	DPyP-Co ^(II) -GO		TEOA (10 vol %)	H ₂ O	300 W Xe lamp	6	1677 μmol g ⁻¹ TOF	62
7	DPyP-Co-GO		TEOA (10 vol %)	H ₂ O	300 W Xe lamp	2	1093 μmol g ⁻¹ TOF	63
8	GO-Sm ^(III) -DPyP		TEOA (16.7 vol %)	H ₂ O	300 W Xe lamp	8	4.39 mmol g ⁻¹ TOF	64
9	PCOF-1	Pt/rGO	EDTA (0.5 M)	H ₂ O	320 W SolarSim, λ > 420 nm		0.75 μmol h ⁻¹ TOF	65
10	exfoliated PCOF-1	Pt/rGO	EDTA (0.5 M)	H ₂ O	320 W SolarSim, λ > 420 nm		1.25 μmol h ⁻¹ TOF	65
11	TPP-GO	Fe-Cat1	cystine (1.8 mM)	EtOH/water (1:24), pH 1.5	Hg lamp (450 W) (λ > 380 nm)	5	1.61 TON	66
12	TPP-GO	Fe-Cat2	cystine (1.8 mM)	EtOH/water (1:24), pH 1.5	Hg lamp (450 W) (λ > 380 nm)	5	1.80 TON	66
13	TPP-GO	Fe-Cat3	cystine (1.8 mM)	EtOH/water (1:24), pH 1.5	Hg lamp (450 W) (λ > 380 nm)	5	2.82 TON	66
14	TPP-GO	Ni-Cat1	AA (0.1 M)	EtOH/water (1:24), pH 4.0	Hg lamp (450 W) (λ > 380 nm)	5	1.2 μL of H ₂	67
15	TPP-GO		TEA (10 vol %)	H ₂ O	UV-vis	6	3.8 μmol mg ⁻¹ TOF	68
16	TPP-GO	Pt	TEA (10 vol %)	H ₂ O	UV-vis	6	4.6 μmol mg ⁻¹ TOF	68
17	TPP-GO/PVP	Pt	TEA (10 vol %)	H ₂ O	UV-vis	6	5.2 μmol mg ⁻¹ TOF	68
18	GO-pTHPP-PSA		TEA	H ₂ O	λ = 450 nm	8	44.3 μmol g ⁻¹ h ⁻¹ TOF	69
19	GQ-dots/Pt-pTHPP		AA (0.1 M)	H ₂ O	λ > 420 nm		57.19 mmol g ⁻¹ h ⁻¹ TOF	71
20	rGO/g-C ₃ N ₄ /Cu/TCPP nanorods		TEOA (20 vol %)	H ₂ O	300 W Xe lamp	5	4 mmol g ⁻¹ TOF	73

Scheme 4. Chemical Structures of (a) Porphyrin Organic Framework PCOF Used by Fan et al.,⁶⁵ (b) TPP–GO Used as a Photosensitizer in Combination with a [Fe–Fe]-Hydrogenase Model or Ni–Cat1 Complex as Catalysts,^{66,67} and (c) Mn–TPP–GO Photocatalyst⁶⁸

(entry 7 in Table 3). The exploration of rare earth metal ions intrigued the researchers to implant Sm^(III) on the surface of graphene oxide, and therefore, they developed and studied the DPyPP–Sm^(III)–GO photocatalytic material.⁶⁴ The interaction of Sm^(III) with the oxygen species of graphene oxide and its coordination with the pyridyl peripheral substitution of DPyPP porphyrin were demonstrated. Photocatalytic investigation showed that the DPyPP–Sm^(III)–GO hybrid reached a H₂ production activity of 4.39 mmol/g after 8 h of visible light

irradiation (entry 8 in Table 3), pointing out the advantageous role of Sm^(III) to the stability and efficiency of the catalytic system.

Fan et al. developed 2D nanodisks comprising exfoliated PCOF-1 (Scheme 4a) through the incorporation of Mg²⁺ and Cu²⁺ ions as well as appropriate axial ligands.⁶⁵ The researchers tested the starting PCOF material and the exfoliated nanodisks in visible-light-driven H₂ evolution, with the latter demonstrating higher activity. The introduction of a co-catalyst material,

Scheme 5. Chemical Structures of (a) Pt-pTHPD Porphyrin Star Polymer⁷¹ and (b) TCPP Used by Li et al.⁷³

namely, Pt/rGO, further improved the catalytic efficiency probably due to high surface interactions between the 2D PCOF nanodisks and the 2D Pt/rGO co-catalyst (entries 9 and 10 in Table 3).

In another report, Li et al. covalently connected GO with tetraphenyl porphyrin via amide coupling to obtain the photosensitizing entity TPP-GO (Scheme 4b), which was used in combination with [Fe-Fe]-hydrogenase models (Scheme 4b) as catalytic entities.⁶⁶ The researchers showed the non-covalent interactions between the catalyst and 2D TPP-GO in aqueous ethanol solution and continued with establishing the catalytic activity of the Fe complexes electrocatalytically. They investigated the photocatalytic activity of the system toward H₂ production utilizing cysteine as the SED and revealed the role of the coordinating ligands on the Fe-Fe catalyst (entries 11–13 in Table 3) as well as the importance of the porphyrin moiety for the absorption in the visible region. Covalent linkage between GO and porphyrin was proven beneficial for the catalytic performance, while GO was also proven essential in enhanced H₂ production, serving as both an electron mediator and a scaffold. This system was further improved by the same research group, who applied TPP-GO as a light-absorbing component and Ni complex (Scheme 4b) as a catalyst in EtOH/H₂O solution using ascorbic acid as the SED (entry 14 in Table 3).⁶⁷ The researchers verified again the importance of all components toward H₂ generation and demonstrated the enhancement of the catalytic activity due to the presence of GO. Besides amide coupling, which was explored in the previous example, GO can be linked with metalated porphyrins through the axial coordination with the metal center. In this concept, Yang and co-workers reported the connection of Mn-TPP porphyrin with GO (Scheme 4c) and used the resulting material in light-driven H₂ production with triethylamine serving as the SED and Pt NPs as catalytic moieties (entries 15–17 in Table 3).⁶⁸ Aggregation was proven a limiting factor in the overall performance of the system and was overcome with the addition of surfactants (PVP, CTAB, and SDS), with non-ionic PVP showing the best results.

Another approach was presented by Li and co-workers, who employed two chromophores to achieve broader photosensitizing ability.⁶⁹ More specifically, the authors grafted pTHPP (Scheme 3a) and pyrene sulfonic acid (PSA; Scheme 4d) onto the surface of graphene oxide utilizing π - π stacking and hydrogen-bonding interactions. The synthesized three-component 2D material, GO-pTHPP-PSA, displayed enhanced photocatalytic H₂ evolution in comparison to the catalytic systems with one or more components absent (entry 18 in Table 3).

Another interesting type of GRM is graphene quantum dots (GQ-dots),⁷⁰ and they were applied in photocatalytic H₂ production in combination with a porphyrin star polymer by Ji et al.⁷¹ More specifically, the authors synthesized polymeric Pt-pTHPD (Scheme 5a) as a catalytic moiety, known for its ability to form micelles⁷² as well as GQ-dots antenna light-harvesting-materials according to a solvothermal procedure. Subsequently, the positively charged Pt-pTHPD micelles self-assembled via electrostatic interactions with the negatively charged GQ-dots and formed a supramolecular photocatalyst GQ-dots/Pt-pTHPD, which reached a very high H₂ production rate under visible light irradiation and displayed enhanced stability (entry 19 in Table 3). One of the latest examples of GRMs and porphyrins applied in the catalytic transformation of protons to molecular hydrogen was reported by Li and co-workers.⁷³ The researchers developed a 2D material consisting of a reduced graphene oxide (rGO)-graphitic carbon nitride (g-C₃N₄) nanocomposite implanted with Cu nanoparticles and self-assembled TCPP (Scheme 5b) nanorods. The cooperative effect of rGO and Cu nanoparticles was proven to be the main reason for the enhanced H₂ evolution that was achieved (entry 20 in Table 3).

The reports reviewed above dealing with photocatalytic H₂ production from porphyrin-graphene ensembles have pointed out the important factors that govern this catalysis, additional to the factors already discussed in the electrocatalytic section. These factors include

- the nature of the porphyrin (i.e., molecular chromophore, polymer, and PCOF)
- the peripheral substitution and metal coordination of the porphyrin, which in most reports is the photosensitizing moiety
- the linkage and interactions (electrostatic and π - π stacking) between the porphyrin molecules and the GRM
- the utilization of appropriate molecules of nanoparticle catalysts and co-catalyst
- the photocatalytic reaction conditions (solvent, pH, and light source)

■ CHALLENGES AND FUTURE PERSPECTIVES

Porphyrins have already been extensively investigated in photo-, electro-, and photoelectrocatalytic H₂ production schemes, while recently, their combination with 2D graphene-based materials has attracted extended scientific attention. The two fundamental remaining challenges include the need for further increased performance and further improved stability to beat commercial processes, like steam methane reforming and electrolysis. GO, rGO, and GQ-dots offer their advanced electronic properties, good stability, and low-cost fabrication,

while porphyrins retain their inherent photophysical and electrochemical characteristics; therefore, the resulting hybrid materials have enhanced activity and prolonged lifespan. This strategy was proven very efficient; thus, other chromophores with alike photophysical features, such as corroles, phthalocyanines, and BODIPY dyes, could also be used as H₂ production catalysts. While porphyrinoids offer significant advantages toward HER, they also have certain limitations, including their susceptibility to degradation under prolonged catalytic conditions due to metal leaching or macrocycle photodegradation. To address the aspect of catalytic stability in the practical application of chromophore–GRM assemblies toward HER, there are strategies such as the incorporation of stabilizing ligands and enhanced binding groups between porphyrinoid and the GRM, which can significantly improve the extended activity.

Moving one step forward, we suggest as future directions the development of dye-sensitized photoelectrochemical cells (DSPECs) utilizing porphyrin–graphene hybrid materials. This approach could advance the overall performance toward H₂ evolution, and it is one step closer to a real-world application because it requires no sacrificial reagents and no externally applied potential. To the best of our knowledge, there is still no report following this strategy for hydrogen generation, while publications concerning other reductive catalytic transformations (i.e., CO₂ reduction) have already been reported.⁷⁴ Noteworthy, other types of 2D materials (i.e., g-C₃N₄) are commonly studied in both photocatalysis and photocurrent response, demonstrating the potential for large-scale implementation.⁷⁵ The combination of traditional steam methane reforming and light-driven hydrogen production is also a promising avenue to follow utilizing porphyrin–graphene hybrid materials.⁷⁶

Another interesting path to investigate would be the utilization of porphene,^{77,78} the porphyrin analogue of graphene, which has only recently been synthesized, exhibits interesting properties, and is still unexplored in hydrogen generation catalysis. Noteworthy, similar 2D materials have been proposed via computational studies as promising single-atom electrocatalysts.⁷⁹ The synthesis of 2D porphene and first raw metalated porphene is expected to open new directions in this field due to the robustness, visible light absorption ability, and catalytic productivity of porphyrin units. One critical area for investigation involves the scalability of such materials. Current methods have been proven efficient at the laboratory scale, but the development of cost-effective, large-scale synthetic routes is crucial for the commercial exploitation of these materials.

CONCLUSION

In the past decade, significant advances have been made in catalytic H₂ production, with the aim of shifting from a fossil-fuel-based economy to a hydrogen economy. This review summarized the recent advances in electrocatalytic and photocatalytic H₂ generation from porphyrin–graphene ensembles. After reviewing all recent publications dealing with electrocatalytic and photocatalytic H₂ production from porphyrin–graphene nanomaterials, we pointed out the important factors that influence this catalytic transformation as well as the role of each catalytic component. The synergy between porphyrin and graphene components resulted in enhanced HER catalytic activity, stability, and efficiency, making them promising candidates for sustainable hydrogen generation. While challenges remain, particularly in scaling up production

and ensuring long-term stability, the future prospects of these materials are bright.

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Notes

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